

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The effect of human resource development on job performance mediated by organizational commitment and job satisfaction on the North Konawe Police Resort Personnel

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the effect of human resource development on organizational commitment, job satisfaction and job performance. To examine the effect of organizational commitment and job satisfaction on job performance and see the mediating role of each organizational commitment and job satisfaction on the influence of human resource development on job performance. This study uses a quantitative approach by taking the research object of Police Personnel at the North Konawe Police Resort. The population of this study amounted to 223 people, then the sample in this study amounted to 143 people, the sampling technique used was simple random sampling. Research data were collected by questionnaire and processed using Partial Least Square (PLS).

The results of this study concluded that human resource development has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on work performance. Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on work performance. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on job performance. Organizational commitment partially mediates the effect of human resource development on work performance. Job satisfaction partially mediates the effect of human resource development on job performance.

Keywords: Human Resource Development; Organizational Commitment; Job Satisfaction; Job Performance

1 Introduction

Managing human resources is a complex matter because humans have very complex characters both in terms of nature and level of behavior shaped by the environment and experience. If management can manage/manage it well, then human resources will put out all their abilities to help realize the goals of the organization. (1) In line with the bureaucratic reforms carried out within the Polri institution, improvements have been made in all fields, especially those related to efforts to carry out the main tasks of the Polri as protectors, protectors and public servants. Therefore, the demands for improvements related to the performance of the police so that they can provide good service to the community are a top priority that must be carried out. The performance of the Police in providing protection, protection and community services is expected to continue to be improved. Likewise, the quality of human resources needs to be developed to improve the ability to carry out their duties properly.

The Police in carrying out their functions and objectives in accordance with the law are supported by their apparatus so that they are directed to districts/cities. Each member in the district/city area is directly responsible to their leader, namely the Resort Police (Kapolres). The North Konawe Resort Police (Polres) as one of the government institutions in

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charge of the North Konawe Regency has a vision of realizing excellent Kamtibmas services in the jurisdiction of the North Konawe Police, which can provide security services and ensure the rule of law and a stable Kamdagri and the establishment of strong police synergies. proactive. To achieve this, an optimal management of human resources and good work performance is needed, including support from personnel from all organizational units within the North Konawe Police work unit.

To achieve the success of an organization is closely related to the quality of the work of its members, so the organization is required to always develop and improve the work performance of its members. Work performance means the work that can be displayed by a member of the organization. Thus, the work performance of a member of the organization can be measured from the work, the results of tasks or the results of activities within a certain period of time (2). The work performance of Polri members is very important in an effort to achieve the goals that have been set in accordance with the vision and mission of the police. Work performance as a police officer is not easy, there are many challenges that must be faced. Police performance can be measured by various aspects, for example in solving a crime case that occurred. The ideal performance of a police officer is to guard, protect and serve the community, but in reality many police officers commit violations.

Human resource development is one of the efforts that indicates a movement towards a better or improved situation for an individual in the organization. One of these development activities is through education and training activities. With the provision of education and training, it is hoped that police members will be able to work more efficiently and be able to carry out their duties better (3). Human resource development has a vital role in efforts to direct, encourage, motivate the improvement/development of the capabilities and skills of human resources which are implemented in their work to achieve the effectiveness of human resources in the organization. Human resource development has a concept for self-development, training programs and career advancement to meet organizational needs for expertise in the future (3).

In addition to work performance, the development of human resources also affects the organizational commitment of the police personnel of the North Konawe Police. Organizational commitment is the level where employees or police personnel believe and are willing to accept the goals of the organization and will stay or will not leave the organization and are willing to work as well as possible to achieve organizational goals (4). The issue of organizational commitment to the North Konawe Police can be seen from the point of view of punishment, in 2021 there will be three cases of punishment given to personnel due to personnel absent from work and immoral cases, this becomes a problem regarding personnel commitment towards the organization and is an indication that there is still a lack of organizational commitment by police personnel at the North Konawe Police Station. In addition, it was also found that there are still personnel who do not try to work well at the North Konawe Police, which makes it necessary to improve in terms of commitment.

The last aspect related to the development of human resources and the achievement of work performance is the achievement of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is one of the most important factors owned by police personnel to get optimal work results. Problems related to job satisfaction within the North Konawe Police Station based on observations made revealed that there are still members who feel that the salary and benefits they receive are not sufficient for their living needs. every member in his division has the desire to get an income that matches their expectations.

2 Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1 Human Resource Development

Human resource development is an activity that must be carried out by an organization to its employees so that their knowledge, abilities, and skills are in accordance with the demands of the work they do. Human resource development is also an effective way to overcome some of the challenges faced by most large organizations (5). In the concept of human resource development, development is defined as an effort to improve the technical, theoretical, conceptual, and moral abilities of employees in accordance with the needs of the job/position through education and training (6). Development is the second operational function of Personnel management where employee development needs to be carried out in a planned and sustainable manner.

In addition, according to (7) states that development includes learning opportunities that aim to further increase the knowledge and skills needed in the work being undertaken. (8) suggests that human resource development is a process of preparing individuals to assume different or higher responsibilities within the organization. Human resource development is usually related to increasing intellectual ability to do a better job. Human resource development is an effort to develop the quality or ability of human resources through the process of education planning, training and

management of personnel or employees to achieve an optimal result (2). Another opinion expressed by (9) that human resource development is a process of planning education, training, and management of employees to achieve an optimal result. Meanwhile, according to (10) development is the withdrawal, selection, development, use, and maintenance of human resources by organizations or institutions.

Human resource development is a process of preparing individuals to assume higher responsibilities related to increasing intellectual abilities to carry out better jobs (11). In the success of an organization, qualified people are needed both in terms of knowledge and skills and mentally (11). Increasing human resources will increase commitment (12). The relationship between these variables is supported by the findings of previous research from (13) which in their research found a positive and significant relationship between human resource development and organizational commitment. In addition, the findings from (14) also conclude the same thing that development in the aspect of human resources will further increase employee engagement with the organization.

Good human resource development encourages employee performance to increase. Every organization must adjust the development of organizational strategy more by relying on the quality of human resources as a key success factor (15). Work performance can be achieved when human resources in an organization have sufficient knowledge, competence and ability to carry out their work (16). The relationship between these variables is supported by the findings of previous research by (17) which in their research looked at the aspects of human resource development for employees of a bank, from the results of this study concluded that the good work performance of employees cannot be separated from how the development of human resources is people made by the organization. Another finding from (18) concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between human resource development on work performance.

According to (19) states that work performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. These work results can be achieved when employees have the appropriate competencies and abilities in completing their work. The process of developing human resources is one way to improve the ability of employees to produce optimal work results. The relationship between these variables is supported by the results of previous research by (18) which in their research revealed that organizational commitment is a good mediation for the development of human resources in relation to improving employee performance.

To measure the human resource development variables in this study, the measurement from (20) will be adopted which measures human resource development activities into five indicators, including (1) job rotation, (2) training and development, (3) planning career, (4) compensation, and (5) performance appraisal.

2.2 Organizational Commitment

The concept of organizational commitment is built on the premise that individuals can form attachments to the organizations they work for. This attachment is characterized by an intention to remain with the organization (identifying with its values and goals), and a willingness to exert extra effort on its behalf (21). Therefore, organizational commitment goes beyond passive loyalty and requires an active relationship with the organization, so that individuals are willing to give something of themselves to contribute to organizational well-being (21). Organizational commitment is one of the most popular topics in the field of management research (22). Organizational commitment is very important for any organization, as it is a good predictor of organizational goals, absenteeism, turnover and productivity (23). Luthans (24) defines organizational commitment as an attitude that reflects employee loyalty to the organization. Henkin et al (25) describe it as a sentiment that encourages workers to become part of the organization and to recognize the goals and values of the organization. Organizational commitment means more than just formal membership, because it includes an attitude of liking the organization and a willingness to put in a high level of effort for the benefit of the organization in order to achieve goals (26). According to (1) organizational commitment is a measure of employee willingness to stay with a company in the future .

The concept of organizational commitment relates to the level of involvement of people with the organization where they work and are interested in staying in the organization. Grenberg et al (27) organizational commitment as a level where individuals identify and engage with the organization and or do not want to leave it. According to (28) organizational commitment is the desire of some workers to remain members of the organization. Organizational commitment affects whether an employee remains as a member of the organization or leaves for another job.

(29) explained that the type of commitment that appears is not only passive loyalty, but also the relationship between employees and the organization, namely the willingness to work to help the organization in achieving its goals. A

committed individual will have his organizational identity, he will work seriously, will be loyal and will have a positive attitude towards his organization. This individual will display behaviors that will help the organization achieve its goals and also want to be part of the organization in the long term. The relationship between these variables is supported by the findings of (18) which in their research found that an increase in organizational commitment possessed by employees will be able to encourage them to work as well as possible and have an impact on increasing work performance.

Measurement of organizational commitment variable in this study will adopt measurements from (30) which consist of (1) Affective Commitment, (2) Continuing Commitment, and (3) Normative Commitment.

2.3 Job satisfaction

Each individual has a different level of job satisfaction according to the value system that applies to him. The higher the perception of job satisfaction according to individual desires, the higher the job satisfaction with these activities. According to (31) revealed that a successful organization is always marked by the fulfillment of job satisfaction. Expectancy theory states that a person's job satisfaction is assessed based on the fulfillment of goals, achievements, realizations, goals and welfare. The more expectations are met, the more satisfied the work will be. Undeniably, job satisfaction is now an important thing to remember in carrying out work activities, every employee is faced with job competition, so they are required to continue to improve the development of job satisfaction. Rivai (32) explains that job satisfaction is basically individual. Each individual has a different level of satisfaction according to the value system that applies to him. The higher the assessment of the work that is felt in accordance with the wishes of the individual, the higher the individual's satisfaction with the job. Job satisfaction is an emotional response to various aspects of one's work. In analyzing a person's job satisfaction, many factors need to be considered. For example, the nature of a person's work has a certain impact on job satisfaction. An employee can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of the job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects.

Job satisfaction for each individual comes from within himself and can show how the quality of a job is. There are various definitions expressed by experts in describing the meaning of job satisfaction. Locke (33) reveals that job satisfaction is often assumed to be a pleasant or positive emotional state resulting from the evaluation or appraisal of one's job or work experience. Meanwhile, (34) defines job satisfaction as a positive attitude and involves a healthy adjustment of employees to work conditions and situations, including financial problems, social conditions, physical conditions and psychological conditions.

Good achievement of organizational goals is reflected in the increased contribution made by human resources. Human Resources, which is reflected in the work of personnel who have worked professionally, with good work placements, of course expect an increase in their work status as evidence of institutional appreciation for their performance (35). So with these various searches, the organization must be able to provide peace, satisfaction and active contribution to personnel. The relationship between these variables is supported by research findings from (13) which conclude that the development of human resources that are in accordance with the needs of the employees themselves will be able to have a positive impact and bring employees to job satisfaction because of the match between training, abilities and knowledge. with the given job. In addition, the findings from (14), also conclude that there is a positive and significant influence between human resource development on job satisfaction.

One of the most important factors to produce optimal work performance . Job satisfaction received and felt by an employee will affect the results obtained from his work. Job satisfaction in any case is very important because the tendency to improve employee performance in the organization will not be achieved without employee job satisfaction (32). The relationship between these variables is supported by the results of previous research by (17) where the research conducted concluded that job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on performance where one aspect of performance is work performance. In addition , the findings of (36) also reveal the same thing that meeting expectations at work can increase employee job satisfaction which in turn will encourage employees to produce better work performance.

The measurement of job satisfaction variable in this study will adopt the measurement from (37) which looks at job satisfaction from the aspects of (1) work regulations, (2) promotion, (3) supervision, (4) additional benefits, (5) communication.

2.4 Work performance

The theory about employee performance in an organization that is influenced by the level of job satisfaction, put forward by (16) that work performance in the organization is influenced by the level of job satisfaction. Productivity and job

satisfaction have a positive or unidirectional relationship, that is, if satisfaction is high, productivity will also be high, and if satisfaction is low, productivity will also be low. This means that organizations with satisfied employees tend to be more effective, than organizations with unsatisfied employees.

Work performance is a person's ability to produce products or services to encourage the achievement of a goal. According to (6) work performance is a work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skills, experience and sincerity and time. Meanwhile, according to (19) work performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. According to (32) work performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in an effort to achieve company goals legally, not violating the law and not contrary to morals or ethics. (38) define work performance as a person's level of proficiency in tasks that include his work, understanding the weight of an individual's ability to fulfill the provisions in the job. (39) also suggests that work performance is more about the level of success achieved by a person to determine the extent to which a person achieves the achievement that is measured or assessed

To measure this variable, this study will adopt the measurement from (40) which measures work performance with 6 key aspects of work performance consisting of (1) work results, (2) job knowledge, (3) initiative, (4) dexterity. mental, (5) Attitude, (6) Discipline of time and absenteeism. From the literature review.

The conceptual framework of this study is shown below

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis is as follow:

- Hypothesis 1: Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment
- Hypothesis 2: Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction
- Hypothesis 3: Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on work performance
- Hypothesis 4: Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on work performance
- Hypothesis 5: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on job performance
- Hypothesis6:Organizational commitment mediates the effect of human resource development on job performance
- Hypothesis 7: Job satisfaction mediates the effect of human resource development on job performance

3 Methods

A quantitative approach was used to statistically confirm the conceptual model designed in this study. Judging from the purpose of the analysis, this research is classified as explanatory research which aims to provide an explanation of the effect of causality between variables and then choose alternative actions. This research was conducted at the Resort Police of North Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province. The population of this research is all police officers who have received human resource development at the North Konawe Resort Police (Polres) totaling 223 people. Then to determine the number of research respondents, the determination of the number of samples will use the formula from (41), based on existing calculations, the sample in this study was obtained with a total of 143 people. The primary data

in this study were collected through a questionnaire which was distributed in two ways , namely by direct distribution to personnel who were found and also through a google form for personnel who could not be found directly . The data collected in this study will be analyzed using Smart-PLS analysis.

4 Results and discussion

In this study, respondents were taken from the Police Personnel at the North Konawe Police Station, amounting to 143 people. Characteristics of respondents in this study were divided into four categories, including gender, last education, years of service and age. Each of these characteristics is described as follows.

In this study, gender was divided into two categories, namely male and female. The details can be seen in the following table.

Table 1 Characteristics Respondent

Category	Number of Respondents (Persons)	Percentage (%)
Gender (M/F)		
Man	141	99
Woman	2	1
Amount	143	100
Education		
SMA/SMK	117	82
S1	25	17
S2	1	1
Amount	143	100
Working Period (Years)		
2 - 9	36	25
10 - 17	34	24
18 - 25	69	48
> 26	4	3
Amount	143	100
Age (Years)		
21 - 27	21	15
28 - 34	20	14
35 - 41	72	50
42 - 48	26	18
> 49	4	3
Amount	143	100

Source: Primary Data Processed, Year 2022

In testing the direct effect there are five hypotheses used in this study. These hypotheses will be tested using the structural equation method with the PLS (Partial Least Square) approach. The results of these studies in detail can be seen in the image below.

Source: Primary Data Processed, Year 2022

Figure 2 Standardized Coefficients Full Model

Table 2 Recapitulation of PLS . Test Results

Direct Influence	Path Coefficient	P Values	Results
H1 : Human Resource Development →Organizational Commitment	0.649	0.000	Received
H2: The bearer of no HR→ Job satisfaction	0.366	0.000	Received
H3: HR holder or HR →Work Performance	0.188	0.023	Received
H4: Organizational Commitment →Work Performance	0.223	0.013	Received
H5: Job Satisfaction Job →Performance	0.398	0.000	Received
Mediation Effect	Path Coefficient	P Values	Results
H6: HR Developers Organizational Commitment →Work →Performance	0.145	0.020	Mediate
H7: HR Manager Job →Satisfaction Job →Performance	0.146	0.000	Mediate

Source: Primary Data Processed, Year 2022

Based on the table recapitulation of existing research results, it can be concluded as follows:

- Based on the results of testing the influence of HR development on organizational commitment, it produces a coefficient value of 0.649 with a P-value of 0.000 (< 0.05). These results indicate that HR development has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment . On this basis, the proposed hypothesis can be accepted.
- Based on the results of testing the influence of HR development on job satisfaction, it produces a coefficient value of 0.366 with a P-value of 0.000 (< 0.05). These results indicate that human resource development has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction . On this basis, the proposed hypothesis can be accepted.
- Based on the results of testing the influence of HR development on work performance , the coefficient value is 0.188 with a P-value of 0.023 (< 0.05). These results indicate that HR development has a positive and significant impact on work performance . On this basis, the proposed hypothesis can be accepted.
- Based on the results of testing the effect of organizational commitment on work performance, it produces a coefficient value of 0.223 with a P-value of 0.013 (< 0.05). These results indicate that organizational

commitment has a positive and significant effect on job performance . On this basis, the proposed hypothesis can be accepted.

- Based on the results of testing the effect of job satisfaction on job performance, the coefficient value is 0.398 with a P-value of 0.000 (< 0.05). These results indicate that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on job performance . On this basis, the proposed hypothesis can be accepted.
- This study examines the mediating effect of organizational commitment on the effect of HR development on job performance . Based on the indirect effect test, it was found that Hypothesis 6 has a path coefficient value of 0.145 and a p-value of 0.020 (< 0.05), so it can be concluded that organizational commitment mediates the effect of HR development on work performance . On this basis, this hypothesis is declared Accepted.
- This research examines the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the effect of HR development on job performance . Based on the indirect effect test, it was found that Hypothesis 7 has a path coefficient value of 0.146 and a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05), so it can be concluded that job satisfaction mediates the effect of HR development on job performance . On this basis, this hypothesis is declared Accepted.

4.1 The effect of human resource development on organizational commitment

Based on the results of hypothesis testing on the effect of human resource development variables on organizational commitment, it was found that human resource development has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This shows that the variable of human resource development is able to explain the increase in organizational commitment. In the tests conducted, it shows a positive and significant effect which means that organizations that carry out development strategies for their human resources, both in terms of increasing work skills and knowledge through training, job rotation, and good career planning are able to encourage members of their organizations to have a commitment to remain are in organizations that are willing to devote their entire tenure to the organization. From these results, it is deemed necessary for organizations, especially the North Konawe Resort Police to always pay attention to their human resource development system so that existing personnel can work well and are willing to continue with the organization.

4.2 The effect of resource development on job satisfaction

Based on the results of hypothesis testing on the effect of resource development on job satisfaction, it was found that human resource development has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This shows that the variable of human resource development is able to explain changes in the increase in job satisfaction of members of the organization. From these results it can be interpreted that the better the process of developing human resources provided by the North Konawe Police to its personnel, the level of satisfaction felt by personnel with what is obtained from their organization will be better. This is supported by the respondent's assessment of good human resource development which includes job rotation, training and development, career planning, compensation and performance appraisals that make personnel feel satisfied with the organization where they work. Based on the results of the path coefficient analysis carried out, it can be seen that the development of human resources has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This means that the better human resource development that is observed from job rotation, training and development, career planning, compensation and performance appraisal can provide an increase in job satisfaction for North Konawe Police personnel.

4.3 The influence of human resource development on work performance

Based on the results of hypothesis testing related to the effect of human resource development on work performance, it was found that human resource development has a positive and significant influence on work performance. This can be interpreted that the better the development of human resources provided by the organization and perceived by the personnel in supporting their work, the better the level of work performance will be. This shows that an increase in the knowledge, skills and work abilities of existing personnel in supporting the optimal work carried out is able to encourage the creation of work performance expected by personnel. Therefore, the process of developing human resources must be carried out optimally so that existing personnel are able to provide satisfactory work results. Based on the results of the path coefficient analysis carried out, it can be seen that the development of human resources has a positive and significant effect on work performance. This means that the better process of developing human resources provided by the North Konawe Police is reflected in good job rotation, providing training and capacity building in accordance with the existing job, good career planning, appropriate compensation and performance appraisal. A good person is able to improve and produce an increase in work performance produced by personnel.

4.4 The effect of organizational commitment on work performance

Based on the results of hypothesis testing related to the effect of organizational commitment on personnel work performance, it was found that organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on work performance. This can be interpreted that the greater the desire and attachment of the personnel to the North Konawe Police, the better the level of work performance will be. These results indicate that the importance of the North Konawe Resort Police is to pay attention to the level of organizational commitment of its personnel so that existing personnel can work better and be serious in achieving the goals of the organization. Organizational commitment is very much needed by the North Konawe Police because police personnel are personnel who have a great responsibility for the creation of security and comfort in the community.

4.5 The effect of job satisfaction on job performance

Based on the results of hypothesis testing related to the effect of job satisfaction on work performance, it was found that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on work performance, so it can be interpreted that the better the job satisfaction felt by personnel to what is given by the North Konawe Police, the higher the level of work performance. the output will be even better. Satisfaction is one of the factors that have a major influence on the creation of work performance which shows that the need for the North Konawe Resort Police to pay attention to every aspect that can create job satisfaction for personnel so that they can work well.

4.6 The effect of human resource development on work performance mediated by organizational commitment

Based on the results of hypothesis testing on the effect of human resource development on work performance mediated by organizational commitment, it was found that organizational commitment mediates the effect of human resource development on job performance. This can be interpreted that the organizational commitment of personnel is a determining factor to improve the work performance of personnel when the process of developing human resources is felt good from the organization. The nature of this organizational commitment mediation is partial mediation which means that with the development of good human resources, it is able to encourage personnel to produce good work performance, and this can be even better when personnel have good organizational commitment. The direct effect of human resource development on work performance found positive and significant results, as well as the indirect effect of human resource development on work performance mediated by organizational commitment also found a positive and significant effect, thus the organizational commitment variable became a partial mediation between human resource development on work performance.

2.1 The effect of human resource development on job performance mediated by job satisfaction

Based on the results of hypothesis testing on the effect of human resource development on job performance mediated by job satisfaction, it was found that job satisfaction mediates the effect of human resource development on job performance. This can be interpreted that job satisfaction is one of the factors that can make the human resource development process carried out by the organization able to produce the expected work performance. The nature of this job satisfaction mediation is partial mediation, which means that job satisfaction is not the main factor that can produce work performance, but the development of human resources that is carried out can also have a direct impact on the achievement of work performance. The direct effect of human resource development on job performance found positive and significant results, as well as the indirect effect of human resource development on job performance with job satisfaction mediation also found a positive and significant effect, thus the job satisfaction variable became a partial mediation between human resource development and work performance.

5 Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion that have been described in the previous chapter , it can be concluded that human resource development has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment of personnel at the North Konawe Police. This means that the better the human resource development process obtained by the personnel, the higher the organizational commitment of the personnel will be . Human resource development has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of personnel at the North Konawe Police Station. This means that the better the human resource development process received by the personnel, the higher the job satisfaction they feel will be. The development of human resources has a positive and significant effect on the work performance of the personnel at the North Konawe Police Station. This means that the better the process of developing human resources received by personnel from the organization, the better the work performance they produce will be.

Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on the work performance of personnel at the North Konawe Police Station. This means that the better the organizational commitment of the personnel, the higher the work performance will be. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the work performance of personnel at the North Konawe Police Station. This means that the better the level of satisfaction felt by personnel with their work, the resulting work performance will also increase. Organizational commitment mediates the effect of human resource development on the work performance of personnel at the North Konawe Police Station. The nature of the mediation is partial mediation, which means that the development of good human resources is able to improve the work performance of the personnel which is triggered by an increase in the organizational commitment of the personnel. Job satisfaction mediates the effect of human resource development on the work performance of personnel at the North Konawe Police Station. The nature of the mediation is partial mediation, which means that the development of good human resources provided by the organization is able to increase work performance which is triggered by increasing job satisfaction felt by personnel. For further researchers, they can re-test using the same variables and relationships or can see the partial effect of each variable on work performance to determine the role of each variable.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Kaswan. Psikologi Industri dan Organisasi. In: Cetakan 1. Bandung: Alfabeta; 2017.
- [2] Notoatmodjo S. Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia. In Jakarta: Rineka Cipta; 2003.
- [3] Kurniawan AW. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Dan Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja, Motivasi Kerja, Dan Kinerja Karyawan Bank Sulselbar. EKUITAS (Jurnal Ekon dan Keuangan). 2012;16(4):391.
- [4] L. Mathis, Robert & H. Jackson J. Human Resource Management. (edisi 10). Jakarta: Salemba Empat; 2011.
- [5] Moekijat. Manajemen personalia dan sumber daya manusia. Bandung: Mandar Maju; 1995.
- [6] Hasibuan MS. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta: PT Bumi Askara; 2011.
- [7] Siagian, Sondang. P. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Edisi Pert. Jakarta: Binapura Aksara; 2008.
- [8] Singodimedjo M. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Surabaya: SMMAS; 2000.
- [9] Gomes FC. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Cetakan Ke. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi; 2000.
- [10] French W. The Personel Management Process USA. . Ohio; South Western: A Division of Thomson Learning; 2005.
- [11] Areros TGTWA, Rumawas W. Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia dan Komitmen Organisasional terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Sinar Terang Mandiri. J Chem Inf Model. 2020;53(9):1689–99.
- [12] Oliveira HH, Honório LC. Human resources practices and organizational commitment: Connecting the constructs in a public organization. Rev Adm Mackenzie. 2020;21(4).
- [13] Kim B, Kim BG. Job satisfaction and organizational commitment and effect of HRD in logistics industry. J Distrib Sci. 2020;18(4):27–37.
- [14] ABUJUDEH S. the Role of Human Resource Management in Employees' Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment. SEA Pract Appl Sci [Internet]. 2019;7(2):137–45. Available from: <http://ezproxy.umgc.edu/login?url=https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=asn&AN=141187787&site=eds-live&scope=site>
- [15] Zuleha Gultom WDS. Pengaruh Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia Terhadap Prestasi Kerja Pegawai Pada Dinas Sumber Daya Air , Tata Kelola Hak Cipta Dan Tata Ruang Provinsi Sumatera Utara. Movere J. 2021;3(2):70–9.
- [16] Robbins SP. Manajemen. In: Edisi Kese. Penerbit Erlangga; 2009.

- [17] Sembiring H, Kiki FF. Consequent Of The Human Resource Development and Job Satisfaction: Empirical Study on PT Bank BNI Medan. *Int Rev Manag an Mark*. 2018;8(4):32–5.
- [18] Labetubun MR, Dewi IGAM. Organizational Commitment: It's Mediating Role in the Effect of Human Resource Management Practices and Workplace Spirituality on Employee Performance. *Eur J Bus Manag Res*. 2022;7(2):112–23.
- [19] Mangkunegara AP. Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan. In Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya; 2015.
- [20] Et.al SM. The Effect of Human Resource Management Practices on Employee Performance. *Turkish J Comput Math Educ*. 2021;12(3):2900–11.
- [21] Porter LW, Steers RM, Mowday RT, Boulian P V. Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *J Appl Psychol*. 1974;59(5):603–9.
- [22] Wasty S. Psikologi Pendidikan. In Jakarta: Rineka Cipta; 2003.
- [23] Bushra F, Usman A, Naveed A. Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employees ' Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment in Banking Sector of Lahore (Pakistan). ... *J Bus Soc Sci [Internet]*. 2011;2(18):261–8. Available from: http://www.ijbssnet.com/journals/Vol_2_No_18_October_2011/31.pdf
- [24] Luthans F. Prilaku Organisasi. Edisi 10. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi; 2006.
- [25] Henkin, A. B., & Marchiori DM. Empowerment and Organizational Commitment of Chiropractic Faculty. *J Manip Physiol Ther*. 2003;
- [26] Steers, RM dan Porter, L. W. Motivation and Work Behaviour. New York: Academic Press.; 2011.
- [27] Greenberg, Jerald RAB. Behavior in Organization. 9 edition. New Jersey: Pearsin Prentice Hall; 2008.
- [28] Colquitt, Jason A, Jeffery A. LePine and MJW. Organizational Behavior. New York: Mc Graw-Hill companies. Inc; 2011.
- [29] Mowday, R. T., Porter, L. W., & Steers RM. Employee Organization Linkages. Texas: South-Western: Cengage Learning.; 2009.
- [30] Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J., & Smith CA. Commitment to organizations and occupations: Extension and test of a three-component conceptualization. *J Appl Psychol*. 1993;78((4)):538–551.
- [31] Renyut BC, Modding HB, Bima J, Sukmawati S. The Effect of Organizational Commitment, Competence on Job Satisfaction and Employees Performance in Maluku Governor's Office. *IOSR J Bus Manag*. 2017;19(11):18–29.
- [32] Rivai V. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan : Dari Teori Ke Praktik. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada; 2004.
- [33] Locke EA. What Is Job Satisfaction? *Organizational Behavior and Human performance*. 1969;4:309–36.
- [34] As'ad M. Seri Ilmu Sumber Daya Manusia. In Yogyakarta: Liberty; 1999.
- [35] Sari Pascariati Kasman P. PENGARUH PENGEMBANGAN SUMBER DAYA MANUSIA DAN RELIGIUSITAS TERHADAP KINERJA KARYAWAN DENGAN KEPUASAN KERJA SEBAGAI VARIABEL INTERVENING PADA BANK SYARIAH INDONESIA (BSI) DI KOTA PADANG. *J Ekon Manaj Sist Inf*. 2021;2(6):714–28.
- [36] Alsafadi Y, Altahat S. Human Resource Management Practices and Employee Performance: The Role of Job Satisfaction. *J Asian Financ Econ Bus*. 2021;8(1):519–29.
- [37] Spector PE. Industrial and Organizational Psychology. Research a. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.; 2000.
- [38] Bernardin HJ and R. Human Resource Management. New York: McGraw-Hill; 2010.
- [39] Prabowo H. Psikologi Komunikasi. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya; 2005.
- [40] Sutrisno E. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Jakarta: Kencana; 2016.
- [41] Supriyono M. No Title. In: Buku Pintar Perbankan. Yogyakarta : CV. Andi Offse; 2011.